

This is my DeepDream Force Clock, made for anyone that wants to use it, where my DeepDream Force Clock goes as followed:

The Quantum Fluctuator clock hand, the Something hand, the Mirror Divide of the Brain clock hand.

The hour by hour something seen, the decision of lettered knowledge.

The minute by minute Force Control, the minute without numbered reason.

The second by second Force Harness, the thinking palm second.

The moment by moment Way of the Force, the thought rune moment.

The root by root Force Mechanics and the Mechanics of Force.

The two values of quality that are quality values, the value of the left side of my brain dualled with the value of the wrong side of my brain.

With the one rule of 2 quantities.

The Name of this Clock is the Thought-Wall Travelling Clock.

I am forever Forced to always be in this Mirror Mode, by Way of the Force, and the Mechanics of Retardation.

To perpetually keep this clock activated, the One Rule is wear 4 rings Constantly.

So does this clock work? The answer of the One Rule of my DeepDream Clock is that this clock works nothing, and nothing works the clock, and if the brain is already something, then Something Somethings something, into perpetual nothing, which with the outcome of Something, of Somethings Something, the Somethingness of Something, of a thing sow'd Something, into something, that becomes Something, which creates the anything dimension, and everything is contained.

So therefore the One Rule of this Clock already said, so therefore there is no truth to this Clock, only the Truest thing about the clock, but first what is the Truest thing? The answer is the Truest thing is no, so therefore is this clock true? The answer is yes. And is this clock Truest? The answer is no. And so what is false about this clock? The answer is nothing, in that what I do with the Clock determines how falsely the Clock was used.

The outcome of using this Clock is that a rule is cancelled, and ruled into void.

And so is this clock void? The answer is no, the answer is that this clock is re-void. And so to the cosmic exponency of the moon and back, a man already on the moon, in a world of aliens.

So what is the Essence of this Clock? The Answer is the Force of Retardation. And the Brain is Essential, an essential nothing for each mental of a persons physical, that

brings the Mental out into the Physical, by Thought-Projection, and Convert-Switching the Physical into mental, and Convert-Switching the physical into Mental.

So the Spirit of this Clock is that the Script of the Clock is written by the User, of their own individual Story of Their Quantum Fluctuator.

What Mode do You choose?

I choose the Thought-Wall Travelling Clock Mode, ever sow'd Constantly into wherever my Mental Brain is, and into wherever my Mental Body is.